

Uric Acid Lowering to Prevent Kidney Function Loss in Diabetes: PERL Allopurinol Study

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Abstract

Significant morbidity and mortality is caused by diabetic kidney disease in people around the globe with type 1 diabetes. Previously, intensive focus was on blood pressure and glucose control which proved to be less effective and as a failure in preventing the progression of the disease and curbing it. Multiple studies have shown the significance of lowering uric acid levels in treating diabetic kidney disease and preventing its progression. This review paper includes a trial conducted by the Preventing Early Renal Function Loss (PERLO Consortium using allopurinol, in lowering the uric acid level and stating that such novel interventions must be tested for positive outcomes. Although the trial targeted diabetes type 1 patients, but the use of allopurinol as a renoprotective agent was found effective in a large number of population. It is inexpensive, safe to use and is cost effective for patients who are at lower risk and going through initial disease stages.

Keywords: Uric Acid, Kidney Function loss

Introduction

In the past 20 years, a prominent progress has been witnessed by the clinicians in the management of type 1 diabetes by maintaining healthy glucose levels and blood pressure along with the use of drugs to inhibit rennin-angiotensin aldosterone system (RAAS). Such improvements have aided in delaying the complication developments in diabetic patients, but the overall incidence of ESRD has not been decreased and DN (diabetic nephropathy) has remained one of the major reasons of high rate of morbidity and mortality. Thus, it has become imperative to test novel strategies which can lead to promising results. ^{1,2}

Multiple studies have shown that increased serum uric acid levels are greatly linked with the risk of subsequent DN events including decline of GFR, onset of albuminuria and its progression in T1D. This observational data was gathered from laboratory analysis and the hypothesis was presented stating that decline in serum uric acid level plays positive role in slowing the GFR decline rate in patients of T1D prone to DN. ^{3,4}

Diabetic Nephropathy: Uric Acid a Potential Pathogenic Factor

Recent studies have revealed strong evidence that uric acid levels define the development of DN and aids in loss of kidney functioning in diabetic patients. In order to get some more evidence, a randomized blind study was conducted on a number of patients. ^{5, 6} In 356 non-proteinuric type 1 diabetic patients (in a foreign general hospital), prediction of GFR loss was given with preserved renal function (eGFR \geq 60 ml/min) who weren't administered with allopurinol at baseline. Serum cystatin C determines eGFR over a period of some time. The study was conducted on two groups of people on the basis of early GFR presence (n= 80) and absence (n= 276), where eGFR was defined as decline $>3.3\%$ per year. Patients with longer T1D showed early GFR loss with high urinary AER and were old. Importantly, these patients showed high serum uric acid levels at baseline in comparison to those patients who had normal renal functions. Moreover, between baseline serum uric acid levels and risk of GFR loss, a 'dose-response relationship' was observed. With every mg/dl increase in serum uric acid level the risk of GFR loss was increased, this showed 2.4 fold increase of early GFR loss with uric acid level increase beyond the set point (4.5 mg/dl). ^{7,8}

Studies have further shown that the transition from normo to micro or macro albuminuria along with the subclinical atherosclerosis progression in Coronary Artery Calcification (CACTI) in Type 1 Diabetes is owing to the serum uric acid level. When it was studied in 323 participants, with every 1 mg/dl rise in baseline serum uric acid, the chances of micro or macroalbuminuria after 6 years also increases by 80%. In an inception cohort study including 264 individuals with a recent T1D diagnosis, it was observed that serum uric acid became a significant independent risk factor for macroalbuminuria, for every 100 umol/L or 1.7 mg/dl rise in uric acid. Moreover, in CACTI it was found that rise in serum uric acid level also acted as a contributory factor in the progression of this disease and other known cardiovascular diseases.

These observations are quite helpful in explaining the rise of metabolic syndrome among young individuals who are prone to ESRD owing to T1D, obesity and metabolic syndrome. Increased levels of serum uric acid are linked with metabolic syndrome and over production or under production can cause hyperuricemia.^{9,10}

When the DN risk factors were studied, potential confounders strongly emphasized upon the role of serum uric acid levels in the pathogenesis of DN and the deterioration of kidney functions in T1D. population based studies supported this hypothesis. A hypothesized pathogenic mechanism showed that how elevated uric acid in kidney disease and cause alterations to nitric oxide pathways (NO), increased oxidative stress and induction of pro inflammatory cytokines. In addition, uric acid levels can cause increased CRP, decreased NO production and induction of cyclooxygenase. It can not only just suppress NO production but can also deplete it completely.

Lowering of Serum Uric Acid

If the increased levels of serum takes part in loss of kidney functions in diabetic patients and also is a risk factor for multiple other diseases, including CVD, then lowering its levels will definitely bring a positive outcome upon the health of the patients.

The availability of the drug, allopurinol makes this hypothesis interesting and testable, characterized by proved efficacy, good safety levels and low cost in comparison to generic drug.

Allopurinol (1,5-dihydro-4H-pyrazolo [3,4-d]pyrimidin-4-one) is an xanthine oxidase inhibitor, it is the enzyme responsible for the conversion of hypoxanthine to xanthine and then xanthine to uric acid. Since 1964, this drug is in the market for the therapy of gout or symptomatic hyperuricemia and cancer treatment/ asymptomatic hyperuricemia and for uric acid kidney stones. The average dose of allopurinol 300 mg/ day causes 30 to 40% serum uric acid reduction, but 60% reduction can only be achieved with 600 mg/day usage. Moreover, lowering of uric acid reverses the many negative physiological effects like reduced oxidative stress, suppression of RAAS, endothelial function, improved NO bioavailability and decline in inflammatory biomarkers.^{11,12}

As kidneys can eliminate allopurinol so it can be used in patients with improper renal functioning. However, up to 30% of the patients report about skin rashes, which are the adverse effects of this drug. After rashed severe hypersensitivity reactions like exfoliative lesion and Stevens-Johnson syndrome (SJS) can follow up, but these are very scarce only 1 out of 10,000. Other potential adverse effects include hepatotoxicity, gout flares and very rare chances of bone marrow depression. Newer agents like xanthine oxidase inhibitor febuxostat can aid in gaining effective lower levels of uric acid which have similar anti-inflammatory and neurohormonal effects compared to allopurinol. As febuxostat is not linked with any skin reactions so it is under trials for CVD issues.

Two small trials gave positive results for the use of allopurinol to lower the risk of kidney function loss. In these studies, 1st group consisted of 52 people, 25% with diabetes who had serum creatinine of 1.35–4.5 mg/dl and a serum uric acid >7.6 mg/dl. Treatment was carried out for one year with allopurinol 100 to 300 mg/day. When the treatment ended, 16% of the subjects had worsening of their kidney functions as compared to 46% subjects in the placebo arm.

In the second study, 114 patients were added, 37% of them diabetes who had GFR <60 ml/min and stable renal function <50% serum creatinine increase in 3 months. These participants were also treated with allopurinol for 1 years with 100 mg/ day dose. At the end of the treatment, GFR was increased on average by 1 ml/min versus 3 ml/min loss in the placebo arm. Together these two studies showed that allopurinol can halt the progression of kidney disease to some extent.

However, these trials had their own limitations. The sample size was small, generalizability of their results was murky, and due to inclusion criteria of serum uric acid levels >7.6 mg/dl, the participants had high uric acid levels (10 mg/dl). The second group was relatively old age (71 average age), and more importantly the kidney disease was quite heterogenous and diabetic nephropathy was present in only a minority of patients.¹³

Study of Test Group

A group was taken for detail studying under specific conditions and medical limitations. In this group 400 subjects were added who were at higher risk of GFR loss owing to the presence of high serum uric acid (≥ 4.5 mg/dl), and micro or macroalbuminuria. In these subjects, the renal function was mildly decrease (GFR=45–100 ml/min/1.73 m²). On the basis of the following considerations, these subjects were focused:

1. Type 1 Diabetes: The link between GFR and uric acid was only demonstrated in T1D patients. It can be present in T2D patients, but the study was limited to the former type.
2. GFR in the 45–100 ml/min/1.73 m² range. Two fold interval was focused. First, nephropathy is at the initial stage where intervention will be beneficial for delaying ESRD. Second, this stage was at such levels where “GFR decliners” could work where renal function had started to decline and on whom clinical trial could be carried out for practical length. Although not so among non-diabetics, 100 ml/min/1.73 m² is a relatively low value for people with T1D.
3. Microalbuminuria is one of the strongest predictors of renal failure in the future. Therefore the subjects with increased urinary albumin excretion were also considered.
4. Serum uric acid ≥ 4.5 mg/ml. this value was used as a set point indicator where a rise above this value showed 2.4 fold increase in odds of renal failure or functional decline.

- **Study Outcomes to be observed**

The primary outcome for the measure of intervention at the end of the study was GFR rate. With this approach, beneficial impacts of intervention upon the kidney functions, its rate of decline such as ESRD or even serum creatinine doubling was observed. Median urinary AER during the last three months of the intervention treatment showed the positive and negative impacts. Cardiovascular disease risk factors were also observed.¹⁴

The use of allopurinol to lower the uric acid levels in order to delay kidney function loss in T1D is still under trial testing, more evidence is needed to finalize its use for the treatment and general medical recommendation.

Conclusion:

Diabetic nephropathy and End Stage Renal Disease continue to pose a major hurdle in attaining the goal of morbidity and mortality reduction in people with T1D. BP and glycemic control and the use of RAAS blockade failed to significantly curb this issue and a dire need of novel approaches raised. The multiple observations showed that serum uric acid has association with the kidney disease progression in T1D. Strong evidence supported the trial based tests of allopurinol to lower the serum uric acid levels.

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